

Molecular phylogeny of tick species in naturally infested cattle

Ola A. Aggar¹, Haider H. Alsaedi¹ and Hasanain A.J. Gharban^{2,*}

¹ Department of Parasitology, College of Veterinary Medicine, University of Wasit, Wasit, Iraq.

² Department of Internal and Preventive Veterinary Medicine, College of Veterinary Medicine, University of Wasit, Wasit, Iraq.

World Journal of Biology Pharmacy and Health Sciences, 2025, 22(03), 107–117

Publication history: Received on 03 April 2025; revised on 30 May 2025; accepted on 02 June 2025

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjbphs.2025.22.3.0499>

Abstract

Background: Tick is the second largest vector of diseases, which infests many domestic and wild animals resulting in great economic losses due to morbidities and mortalities.

Aim: Clinical investigation of naturally infested cattle found in Al-Diwanyah city (Al-Qadisiyah, Iraq), morphological diagnosis of ticks' species, and molecular phylogeny of local isolates to identify its identity to global NCBI-GenBank isolates.

Materials and methods: Totally, 438 cattle of different ages and sexes were examined clinically during June-July (2024) to identify and collection of tick samples to be examined traditionally based on morphological characterization. Then, the tick samples were examined molecularly using the conventional PCR, and some of positive samples were sequenced, submitted in the NCBI-database and analysed phylogenetically using the MEGA-11 Software.

Results: A total of 72.37% of study cattle were infested clinically with ticks that existed high significantly in hind-limbs (97.48%) and ears (91.17%), but reduced in back (14.51%) when compared to other body parts including neck (79.2%), udder (71.92%), perineum (52.68%), and forelimbs (35.96%). Regarding age, the prevalence rate of tick was increased significantly in cattle aged 6-9 years (96.72% [59/61]) and cattle aged ≥ 10 years (96.3%) and decreased significantly in cattle aged ≤ 1 year (15.22%) in comparison with those aged 2-5 years (84.5%). Among the positive infested animals, ticks were detected significantly in cattle aged 2-5 years (68.77%) and decreased in those aged ≤ 1 year (4.42%) and ≥ 10 years (8.2%) when compared to cattle aged 2-5 years (18.61%). Based on their morphology, microscopic characteristic suspected largely that all collected samples were hard ticks and belong to *Hyalomma anatolicum*. Targeting the 18S rRNA gene, the PCR results confirmed that all samples are belonged to *H. anatolicum*. The sequence data of 11 local isolates were named as "Ghirban-Iraq1 to Ghirban-Iraq11", and submitted in the NCBI-GenBank database under the accession numbers "PV615532.1 to PV615542.1". Phylogenetic analysis of study isolates revealed its significant identity to the global NCBI-BLAST Chinese *H. anatolicum* XJ076 isolate (JX051052.1) at a similarity ranged 98.65-99.87% with presence of mutation / changes at 0.017-0.0011%.

Conclusion: Hard ticks, especially *H. anatolicum*, remain a high prevalent ectoparasite in Iraqi cattle causing severe economic losses due to morbidities and mortalities. The combination of traditional morphological characteristics and molecular phylogeny revealed a high efficacy in identification of tick species. Therefore, we recommended to collection the ticks from all field animals to investigate the tick species based on their morphology, and demonstrating their species and origins following the molecular phylogeny due to the definite role of this external parasite in transmission of various diseases to both animals and humans.

Keywords: Ixodid; Cattle Ectoparasites; *Hyalomma Anatolicum*; Polymeras Chain Reaction (PCR); 18s rRNA Gene; Iraq

* Corresponding author: Hasanain A.J. Gharban

1. Introduction

Tick is an ectoparasite of marked distribution, and considers the second largest vector of diseases in the world as infects many wild and domestic animals in several tropical and subtropical areas, resulting in great economic losses caused by morbidities and mortalities (Brites-Neto et al., 2015; Boulanger et al., 2019). Ticks scientific organization of three families are, Argasidae (soft), Ixodidae (hard) and Nuttalliellidae (Monotypic) which is a member of the Ixodida Order belonging to the Arthropoda phylum (Kelava et al., 2021). Hard ticks referred to so because of scutum's presence on their bodies are the most common and important bearer of pathogens as they took one, two or three hosts while its life cycle had four stages; egg, larva, nymph and adult (Apanaskevich, et al., 2014; Kahl, 2018; Okely, et al., 2021). Globally, spread of infectious diseases are more and more compromising the health of the global population as the number of affected people continues to increase, hence, better understanding of interactions, vectors and pathogens can help in development of prevention and control strategies (De la Fuente et al., 2017; Bouchard et al., 2019).

For diagnosis, the primary methods usage, such as macroscopic and microscopic examination to define tick may provide unconfirmed results in case of the absence epidemiological history (Kemal et al., 2016). In a study of differentiation of some of *Hyalomma apanaskevich*, Horak (2006) revealed that the detection based on the morphological characteristics such size and color of the scutum of different tick stages is extremely complicated and requires great expertise. In addition, differentiating of tick species based on the morphology may lead to misclassification specifically when the method of collecting ticks is so damaging that they get physically hurt due to low expertise and engorging ticks with blood (Estrada-Pena et al., 2017; Nava et al., 2017). For this reason, DNA based methods like polymerase chain reaction (PCR) assays are precise diagnostic methods this offers a real valuable very sensitive and valid information in particular facing epidemiological research (Lv et al., 2014 a, b; Amira et al., 2021). In Iraq however studies have been made on characterization and distribution of ticks on various animal species (Al-gharban and Dhahir, 2015). Based on the works of other studies, these data are under expected since ticks and their incriminated diseases still exist in bigger numbers (Mohammad, 2015; Al-Fatlawi and Al-Fatlawi, 2019; Ali et al., 2021). Hence, this study aims to clinical investigation of naturally infested cattle found in Al-Diwanyah city (Al-Qadisiyah, Iraq), morphological diagnosis of ticks' species, and molecular phylogeny of local isolates to identify its identity to global NCBI-GenBank isolates.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Samples

Totally, 438 cattle of different ages and sexes were examined clinically during June-July (2024) to identify and collection of tick samples in various areas in Al-Diwanyah city (Al-Qadisiyah, Iraq). The tick samples of each infested animal were sprayed by ethanol 70% and collected by rotating manner using of forceps to avoid damaging of their mouthparts, and then, kept into labeled plastic containers that transported cooled using ice-box. In laboratory, ticks of each sample were divided into two parts, one for morphology which saved cooled and the other for molecular assay which saved frozen.

2.2. Morphological Identification

Tick samples were identified microscopically in the Iraqi Natural History Research Center and Museum (University of Baghdad, Baghdad, Iraq) based on the reference classification keys of other researchers (Walker et al., 2003; Estrada-Pena et al., 2004).

2.3. Molecular analysis

Following the manufacturer instructions of the AddPrep Genomic DNA Extraction Kit (AddBio, Korea), DNAs were extracted from the ticks, and checked for its concentration and purity using the Nanodrop System (Thermo Fisher, USA). Targeting the *18S rRNA* gene, one set of primers [(F: 5'-GCAAAAGGAGCCGTTTCGTTT-3') and (R: 5'-GACAGACGAAGCCAAGGGAA-3')] was designed based on sequence data of the NCBI global *Hyalomma anatolicum* isolate (JQ737105.1) and used to preparing the MasterMix (AddBio, Korea) tubes at a final volume of 20 µl. For PCR reaction, the thermocycler conditions were included 1 cycle (94°C, 7min) for initial denaturation, 35 cycles for denaturation (94°C, 45sec), annealing (58°C, 45sec) and extension (72°C, 1min), and 1 cycle for final extension (72°C, 10min). Electrophoresis using the agarose-gel stained with Ethidium Bromide was done at 80Am, 100volt for 1 hour. The PCR products were visualized using the UV-transilluminator and photographed using the digital camera. The product size of PCR positive samples to *H. anatolicum* were detected at 966bp.

2.4. Phylogenetic analysis

The DNAs of some positive *H. anatolicum* samples were selected and sent to the MacroGen Company (Korea). The received sequence data were submitted initially in the NCBI-GenBank database to get the specific access numbers for the local *H. anatolicum* study isolates, and then subjected to the multiple sequence alignment analysis and phylogenetic tree analysis in the MEGA-11 Software to identify its identity to the NCBI-BLAST *H. anatolicum* isolates (Al-Graibawi et al., 2021).

2.5. Statistical analysis

One-Way ANOVA in the GraphPad Prism (version 6.0.1) Software were applied to detect significant variation between values of study groups at $P < 0.05$ (*) and $P < 0.01$ (**), (Gharban et al., 2023, 2023).

3. Results

A total of 72.37% (317 / 438) of study cattle were detected clinically to be infested with different species and numbers of ticks; whereas, 27.63% (121/438) were seen to be free of ticks (Figure 1).

The tick isolates were existed high significantly (p -value = 0.0015; 95%CI = 35.24 to 91.31) in hind-limbs [97.48% (309/317)] and followed by ears [91.17% (289/317)], but reduced significantly in back [14.51% (46/317)] when compared to other body parts including neck [79.2% (251/317)], udder [71.92% (228/317)], perineum [52.68% (167/317)], and forelimbs [35.96% (114/317)] (Figure 2). Regarding age of study cattle, the findings showed that the prevalence rate of tick was increased significantly (p -value = 0.0332; 95%CI = 11.04 to 135.3) in cattle aged 6-9 years [96.72% (59/61)] and cattle aged ≥ 10 years [96.3% (26/27)] and decreased significantly in cattle aged ≤ 1 year [15.22% (14/92)] in comparison with those aged 2-5 years [84.5% (218/258)] (Figure 3). Among the positive infested animals, ticks were detected significantly (p -value = 0.0192; 95%CI = 22.40 to 72.40) in cattle aged 2-5 years [68.77% (218/317)] and decreased in those aged ≤ 1 year [4.42% (14/317)] and ≥ 10 years [8.2% (26/317)] when compared to cattle aged 2-5 years [18.61% (59/317)] (Figure 4).

Figure 1 Total results of clinical examination to detect the ticks in totally 438 study cattle

Figure 2 Distribution of ticks on the body regions of infested cattle (total number = 317)

Figure 3 Association of tick infestation to age of study cattle (total number = 438)

Figure 4 Association of tick infestation to age of positively infested cattle (total number = 317)

Figure 7 Multiple sequence alignment of the local and NCBI-BLAST *H. anaticum* isolates/strains using NCBI MSA Viewer

Table 1 Homology Sequence identity (%) for local and NCBI-BLAST *H. anatolicum* isolates

Local isolate		NCBI isolate				
Name	Access No.	Species	Isolate	Country	Access No.	%
Ghirban-Iraq1	PV615532.1	<i>H. anatolicum</i>	XJ076	China	JX051052.1	99.87
Ghirban-Iraq2	PV615533.1	<i>H. anatolicum</i>	XJ076	China	JX051052.1	99
Ghirban-Iraq3	PV615534.1	<i>H. anatolicum</i>	XJ076	China	JX051052.1	98.97
Ghirban-Iraq4	PV615535.1	<i>H. anatolicum</i>	XJ076	China	JX051052.1	99.22
Ghirban-Iraq5	PV615536.1	<i>H. anatolicum</i>	XJ076	China	JX051052.1	99.62
Ghirban-Iraq6	PV615537.1	<i>H. anatolicum</i>	XJ076	China	JX051052.1	99.75
Ghirban-Iraq7	PV615538.1	<i>H. anatolicum</i>	XJ076	China	JX051052.1	98.98
Ghirban-Iraq8	PV615539.1	<i>H. anatolicum</i>	XJ076	China	JX051052.1	99.10
Ghirban-Iraq9	PV615540.1	<i>H. anatolicum</i>	XJ076	China	JX051052.1	98.65
Ghirban-Iraq10	PV615541.1	<i>H. anatolicum</i>	XJ076	China	JX051052.1	99.13
Ghirban-Iraq11	PV615542.1	<i>H. anatolicum</i>	XJ076	China	JX051052.1	99.10

4. Discussion

The findings of this study were in agreement with other local studies such as Suleiman (2018) who recorded 36.77% infested cattle with hard ticks; but higher than those recorded in Sulaimanyia (11.8%) by Kadir et al. (2012); and in Baghdad (8.1%) by Hasson (2012) and 12.9% by Mallah and Rahif (2016); while were lowered than reported in Basrah (42.5%) by AL-Mayah and Abdul-Karim (2020). In comparison with other global studies, the overall prevalence of hard ticks in cattle was 85% in Pakistan (Ali et al., 2013), 67.5% in Iran (Ghashghaei et al., 2017), 40.26% in Ethiopia (Yalew et al., 2017) and 41.93% in India (Debbarma et al., 2018).

Based on their morphology, microscopic characteristic demonstrated that all collected samples were hard ticks and belong to *Hyalomma anatolicum*. Our results were similar with that reported by other researchers (Intirach et al., 2023; Luz et al., 2023).

Targeting the *18S rRNA* gene, the PCR results confirmed that all samples belonged to genus of *Hyalomma anatolicum*.

These results were in agreement with other locally studies carried out in Al-Najaf (Al-Fatlawi et al., 2018) and Babylon (Saadoon and Abid, 2021) provinces. Globally, the findings of this study were similar with that detected in Turkey (Aktas et al., 2006), Tunisia (M'ghirbi et al., 2008), China (Yu et al., 2018), Pakistan (Zeb et al., 2020), Egypt (Amira et al., 2021) and Saudi Arabia (Omer et al., 2021).

Many researchers in Iraq and neighboring countries have studied the epidemiology of persistent ticks and reported that dairy cattle grazing on pastures can become infected with ticks during grazing (Al-gharban and Dhahir, 2015; Desta et al., 2016; Kasaija et al., 2021). In Iraq, six species have been recorded including *Rhipicephalus annulatus*, *R. sanguineus*, *H. anatolicum*, *H. impeltatum*, *H. marginatum* and *H. excavatum* (Omar et al., 2007; Mohammed, 2015; Al-Abidi and Al-Ameri, 2021). An extensive study of some cattle herds in Basra province showed that *H. excavatum* can infect cows, calves and donkeys for the first time in Iraq. *Hyalomma asiaticum* was first recorded in animals in the south Iraq (Awad and Abdul-Hussein, 2006). In northern Iraq, Ismail and Omar (2021) recorded six species in Duhok city which belongs to two major tick genera, three species belonging to *Hyalomma* and three species of minor pollinators belonging to the genus *Rhipiciphalus*. A new species of the subgenus *Hyalomma* (*H. asiaticum asiaticum*) was reported for the first time in the Duhok region. In addition, a study was conducted to determine the prevalence of ticks of the family Ixodidae among horses and some domestic animals in Erbil province (Aziz and AL-Barwary, 2020). Another survey was conducted between September and February 2020 to determine the prevalence of the epidemic in the northern region of Basra province using 250 animal samples of different ages and sexes from the same region (Faraj et al., 2021). In other countries, *H. anatolicum* is well adapted to the dry climates of the Mediterranean and North Africa and other desert climates on both continents (Walker, 2014). In Saudi Arabia, a study on several dairy farms in the Al-Ahsa in the eastern

region found *H. excavatum* (18.33%), *H. dromedarii* (17.63%), *H. anatolicum* (14.29%) and *R. turanicus* (14.04%), *H. impeltatum* (11.28%), *R. Praetexttatus* (8.56%); *H. turanicum* (6.20%), *Haemaphysalis sulcata* (3.57%), *R. kohlsi* (2.33%), *H. rufipes* (2.09%), *H. schulzei* (1.03%), *H. variegatum* (0.47%) and *A. gemma* (0.18%), (Abdally et al., 2020).

5. Conclusion

Hard ticks, especially *H. anatolicum*, remain a high prevalent ectoparasite in Iraqi cattle causing severe economic losses due to morbidities and mortalities. The combination of traditional morphological characteristics and molecular phylogeny revealed a high efficacy in identification of tick species. Therefore, we recommended to collection the ticks from all field animals to investigate the tick species based on their morphology, and demonstrating their species and origins following the molecular phylogeny due to the definite role of this external parasite in transmission of various diseases to both animals and humans.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

Authors thank the College of Veterinary Medicine (University of Wasit, Wasit, Iraq) for all facilities and supports provided during completion of this work.

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

Statement of ethical approval

This study was licensed by the Scientific Committee in the College of Veterinary Medicine (University of Wasit) and performed under the approval No: CVM-UW-4/4/2024-158.

References

- [1] Abdally, M. H., Al-Marri, T. M., Abdally, H. M., and Al-Jabr, O. A. (2020). Incidence and Prevalence of Hard Ticks in Ruminants of Al-Ahsa Oasis Region, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. *World's Veterinary Journal*, 10(3), 276-285.
- [2] Aktas, M., Altay, K., and Dumanli, N. (2006). A molecular survey of bovine *Theileria* parasites among apparently healthy cattle and with a note on the distribution of ticks in eastern Turkey. *Veterinary parasitology*, 138(3-4), 179-185.
- [3] Al-Abedi, G. J. K., and Al-Amery, A. M. A. (2021). Molecular Diagnosis and Phylogenetic Analysis of *Babesia* Species Isolated from Ticks of Infested Cattle in Wasit Governorate, Iraq. *Iraqi Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, 52(1).
- [4] Al-Fatlawi, M. A., Ali, M. J., and Albayati, H. H. (2018). Morphological and phylogenetic study of *Hyalomma anatolicum* in Al-Najaf, Iraq. *Iraqi Journal of Veterinary Sciences*, 32(2), 261-266.
- [5] Al-Fatlawi, M. S. H., and Al-Fatlawi, M. A. A. (2019). Molecular and phylogenetic study of *Theileria* SPP isolated from ticks in AL-Diwaniyah city, Iraq. *The Iraqi Journal of Agricultural Science*, 50(1), 475-479.
- [6] Al-gharban, H. A., and Dhahir, S.H. (2015). Serological diagnosis of persistent infection with *Anaplasma marginale* bacteria in cattle. *The Iraqi Journal of Veterinary Medicine*, 39(1), 33-39.
- [7] Al-Graibawi, M. A., Yousif, A. A., Gharban, H. A., and Zinsstag, J. (2021). First serodetection and molecular phylogenetic documentation of; *Coxiella burnetii*; isolates from female camels in Wasit governorate, Iraq. *Iraqi Journal of Veterinary Sciences (IJVS)*, 35(Suppl. 3), 47-52.
- [8] Ali, M. J., Atiyah, W. R. R., Al-Fatlawi, M. A. A., and Khlaif, S. F. (2021). Genotypic analysis of ticks species infesting cattle in Al-Diwaniyah abattoir. *Iraqi Journal of Veterinary Sciences*, 35(4), 673-677.
- [9] Ali, Z., Maqbool, A., Muhammad, K., Khan, M., and Younis, M. (2013). Prevalence of *Theileria annulata* infected hard ticks of cattle and buffalo in Punjab, Pakistan. *DNA*, 862, 846.
- [10] AL-Mayah, S. H., and Abdul-Karim, A. T. (2020). Epidemiology and seasonal variation of ixodid ticks and Piroplasmida detection in cattle of Basrah province, Iraq. *Indian Journal of Forensic Medicine and Toxicology*, 14(3), 1391-1398.

- [11] Amira, A. H., Răileanu, C., Tauchmann, O., Fischer, S., Nijhof, A. M., and Silaghi, C. (2021). Tick species identification and molecular detection of tick-borne pathogens in blood and ticks collected from cattle in Egypt. *Ticks and Tick-borne Diseases*, 12(3), 101676.
- [12] Apanaskevich, D. A., Oliver, J. H., Sonenshine, D. E., and Roe, R. M. (2014). Life cycles and natural history of ticks. *Biology of ticks*, 1, 59-73.
- [13] Apanaskevich, D.A., and Horak, I.G. (2006). The genus *Hyalomma* Koch, 1844. I. Reinstatement of *Hyalomma* (*Euhyalomma*) *glabrum* Delpy, 1949 (Acari, Ixodidae) as a valid species with a redescription of the adults, the first description of its immature stages and notes on its biology. *Onderstepoort Journal of Veterinary Research*, 73, 1–12.
- [14] Awad, A. H. H., and Abdul-Hussein, M. A. (2006). New record of two species of hard ticks from some domestic animals in Basrah-Iraq. *Journal of Basrah Researches (Sciences)*, 32(1A), 1-6.
- [15] Aziz, K. J., and AL-Barwary, L. T. O. (2020). Molecular identification of *Theileria equi* and *Babesia caballi* from ixodid ticks infesting equids in Erbil province, northern of Iraq. *Adv. Anim. Vet. Sci*, 8(12), 1286-1293.
- [16] Bouchard, C., Dibernardo, A., Koffi, J., Wood, H., Leighton, P. A., and Lindsay, L. R. (2019). Climate change and infectious diseases: The challenges: N increased risk of tick-borne diseases with climate and environmental changes. *Canada Communicable Disease Report*, 45(4), 83-92.
- [17] Boulanger, N., Boyer, P., Talagrand-Reboul, E., and Hansmann, Y. (2019). Ticks and tick-borne diseases. *Medecine et maladies infectieuses*, 49(2), 87-97.
- [18] Brites-Neto, J., Duarte, K. M. R., and Martins, T. F. (2015). Tick-borne infections in human and animal population worldwide. *Veterinary world*, 8(3), 301.
- [19] De la Fuente, J., Antunes, S., Bonnet, S., Cabezas-Cruz, A., Domingos, A. G., Estrada-Peña, A., and Rego, R. O. (2017). Tick-pathogen interactions and vector competence: identification of molecular drivers for tick-borne diseases. *Frontiers in cellular and infection microbiology*, 7, 114-129.
- [20] Debbarma, A., Pandit, S., Jas, R., Baidya, S., Chandra Mandal, S., Sarathi Jana, P., and Das, M. (2020). Prevalence of tick-borne haemoparasitic diseases in cattle of West Bengal, India. *Biological Rhythm Research*, 51(2), 310-317.
- [21] Desta, B. G. E. A. H. (2016). Review on the impact of ticks on livestock health and productivity. *J. Bio. Agr. Health*, 6, 1-7.
- [22] Estrada-Pena, A., D'Amico, G., Palomar, A. M., Dupraz, M., Fonville, M., Heylen, D., and Mihalca, A. D. (2017). A comparative test of ixodid tick identification by a network of European researchers. *Ticks and Tick-borne Diseases*, 8(4), 540-546.
- [23] Faraj, K. B., Saud, S. S., and Almyahii, M. H. (2021). Study of the Common Tick Species of Cattle in the North of Basrah Province. *Annals of the Romanian Society for Cell Biology*, 6740-6748.
- [24] Gharban, H. A., Al-Ghuraibawi, H. N., Al-Rubaye, Z. A., Jahlol, H. A., Al-Zergany, A. A., and Al-Abedi, G. J. (2023). Most Clinically Detected Viral Diseases in Field Animals of Wasit Province, Iraq. *Annals of the Romanian Society for Cell Biology*, 27(01), 154-168
- [25] Ghashghaei, O., FARD, S. R. N., Khalili, M., and Sharifi, H. (2017). A survey of ixodid ticks feeding on cattle and molecular detection of *Coxiella burnetii* from ticks in Southeast Iran. *Turkish Journal of Veterinary and Animal Sciences*, 41(1), 46-50.
- [26] Hasson, R. H. (2012). Tick distribution and infestation among sheep and cattle in Baghdad's south suburb. *Kufa Journal For Veterinary Medical Sciences*, 3(1), 77-90.
- [27] Intirach, J., Lv, X., Han, Q., Lv, Z. Y., and Chen, T. (2023). Morphological and Molecular Identification of Hard Ticks in Hainan Island, China. *Genes*, 14(8), 1592-1605.
- [28] Ismael, S., and Omer, L. T. (2021). Molecular identification of new circulating *Hyalomma asiaticum asiaticum* from sheep and goats in Duhok governorate, Iraq. *Iraqi Journal of Veterinary Sciences*, 35(1), 79-83.
- [29] Kadir, M. A., Zangana, I. K., and Mustafa, B. H. S. (2012). A study on epidemiology of hard tick (Ixodidae) in sheep in Sulaimani governorate-Iraq. *Iraqi Journal of Veterinary Sciences*, 26, 95-103.
- [30] Kahl, O. (2018). Hard ticks as vectors—some basic issues. *Wiener klinische Wochenschrift*, 130(15-16), 479-483.
- [31] Kasaija, P. D., Estrada-Peña, A., Contreras, M., Kirunda, H., and de la Fuente, J. (2021). Cattle ticks and tick-borne diseases: a review of Uganda's situation. *Ticks and Tick-borne Diseases*, 12(5), 101756.

- [32] Kelava, S., Mans, B. J., Shao, R., Moustafa, M. A. M., Matsuno, K., Takano, A., and Nakao, R. (2021). Phylogenies from mitochondrial genomes of 120 species of ticks: Insights into the evolution of the families of ticks and of the genus *Amblyomma*. *Ticks and tick-borne diseases*, 12(1), 101577.
- [33] Kemal, J., Muktar, Y., and Alemu, S. (2016). Distribution and prevalence of tick infestation in cattle in Babille district, eastern Ethiopia. *Livest Res Rural Dev*, 28, 12-21.
- [34] Luz, H. R., Labruna, M. B., Pacheco, R. C., Gianizella, S. L., Nunes, P. H., Szabó, M. P., and Martins, T. F. (2023). Morphological anomalies in hard ticks (Acari: Ixodidae) from Brazil. *Ticks and Tick-borne Diseases*, 14(6), 102219.
- [35] Lv, J., Wu, S., Zhang, Y., Zhang, T., Feng, C., Jia, G., and Lin, X. (2014a). Development of a DNA barcoding system for the Ixodida (Acari: Ixodida). *Mitochondrial Dna*, 25(2), 142-149.
- [36] Lv, J., Wu, S., Zhang, Y., Chen, Y., Feng, C., Yuan, X., and Lin, X. (2014b). Assessment of four DNA fragments (COI, 16S rDNA, ITS2, 12S rDNA) for species identification of the Ixodida (Acari: Ixodida). *Parasites and vectors*, 7, 1-11.
- [37] M'ghirbi, Y., Hurtado, A., Brandika, J., Khlif, K., Ketata, Z., and Bouattour, A. (2008). A molecular survey of *Theileria* and *Babesia* parasites in cattle, with a note on the distribution of ticks in Tunisia. *Parasitology research*, 103, 435-442.
- [38] Mallah, M. O., and Rahif, R. H. (2016). Epidemiological study for ticks infestation in cattle in Baghdad city-Iraq. *AL-Qadisiyah Journal of Veterinary Medicine Sciences*, 15(2), 45-51.
- [39] Mohammad, M. K. (2015). Distribution of ixodid ticks among domestic and wild animals in central Iraq. *Bulletin of the Iraq Natural History Museum (P-ISSN: 1017-8678, E-ISSN: 2311-9799)*, 13(3), 23-30.
- [40] Nava, S., Venzal, J. M., Acuña, D. G., Martins, T. F., and Guglielmone, A. A. (2017). *Ticks of the Southern Cone of America: diagnosis, distribution, and hosts with taxonomy, ecology and sanitary importance*. Academic Press.
- [41] Okely, M., Anan, R., Gad-Allah, S., and Samy, A. M. (2021). Hard ticks (Acari: Ixodidae) infesting domestic animals in Egypt: diagnostic characters and a taxonomic key to the collected species. *Medical and Veterinary Entomology*, 35(3), 333-351.
- [42] Omer, L. T., Kadir, M. A. A., Seitzer, U., and Ahmed, J. S. (2007). A survey of ticks (Acari: Ixodidae) on cattle, sheep and goats in the Dohuk Governorate, Iraq. *Parasitology research*, 101, 179-181.
- [43] Omer, S. A., Alsuwaid, D. F., and Mohammed, O. B. (2021). Molecular characterization of ticks and tick-borne piroplasms from cattle and camel in Hofuf, eastern Saudi Arabia. *Saudi Journal of Biological Sciences*, 28(3), 2023-2028.
- [44] Saadoon, H.H., and Abid, A.J. (2021). *Biochemical And Molecular Study Of Cypermethrine Resistance Gene In Hard Tick In Cattle*. MSc Thesis, College of Veterinary Medicine, University of AL-Qadisiyah, AL-Qadisiyah (Iraq).
- [45] Suleiman, T. S., Karimuribo, E. D., and Mdegela, R. H. (2018). Prevalence of bovine subclinical mastitis and antibiotic susceptibility patterns of major mastitis pathogens isolated in Unguja island of Zanzibar, Tanzania. *Tropical animal health and production*, 50, 259-266.
- [46] Walker, A. R. (2014). Ticks and associated diseases: a retrospective review. *Medical and veterinary entomology*, 28(S1), 1-5.
- [47] Yalew, A., Adugna, S., and Keffale, M. (2017). Identification of major ixodid ticks on cattle in and around Haramaya town, eastern hararghe, Ethiopia. *Acta Parasitol. Glob*, 8(1), 09-16.
- [48] Yu, Q., Lu, C., Li, B., Fang, S., Zuo, W., Dai, F., and Xiang, Z. (2018). Identification, genomic organization and expression pattern of glutathione S-transferase in the silkworm, *Bombyx mori*. *Insect biochemistry and molecular biology*, 38(12), 1158-1164.
- [49] Zeb, J., Shams, S., Din, I. U., Ayaz, S., Khan, A., Nasreen, N., and Senbill, H. (2020). Molecular epidemiology and associated risk factors of *Anaplasma marginale* and *Theileria annulata* in cattle from North-western Pakistan. *Veterinary parasitology*, 279, 109044.